

SPECIAL ISSUE ARTICLE

Determination of essential elements (Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn) in herbal teas by TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES

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The aim of this study was the comparison of the results obtained in the determination of the content of essential elements such as Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in vegetation samples using different analytical approaches, including suspension preparation and total reflection X-ray fluorescence (TXRF) analysis as well as most commonly used spectroscopic methods in the field of vegetal analysis such as acid digestion in combination with atomic emission (AES) and atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS). In the case of TXRF analysis, two instruments equipped with different X-ray tubes anodes (W and Mo) were used to better evaluate the potential of TXRF for vegetal samples analysis. Analytical figures of merit for the considered methods were determined by the analysis of plant reference materials. The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) applied to the analysed and certified values showed that the results were not statistically different at the significance level of p -values <0.05 . Therefore, suspension preparation and TXRF analysis proved to be a sustainable and fast analytical alternative to the most commonly used ones involving a previous digestion of the sample and inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) or flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) analysis. Finally, the different analytical approaches were applied to the determination of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in a set of herbal teas used for medical purposes.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Measurement of elements in herbal teas is of great importance to consumers not only from a nutritional point of view, but also to assess their quality and evaluate the potential risk–benefit ratio of their consumption. The need to monitor the content of elements in plants for human consumption has been highlighted to ensure the quality and safety of these products.^[1–6]

It is well known that trace elements such as Zn, Mn, Cu and Fe are considered essential for humans and play important roles in plant metabolism and biosynthesis depending on their concentration as cofactors for enzymes. Zn, Mn and Fe are important co-enzymes; Cu is bound to amino acids and they are critical components of many antioxidant processes.^[7] In general, the main properties of the essential elements depend on the regulatory mechanisms that keep the elements at nutrient levels, but in high concentrations they can be toxic.^[8] It

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is well known that one of the oldest methods of treating diseases is to take herbal teas. Accordingly, it is important to have good quality control for medicinal herbs to protect consumers health.^[9]

As awareness and concern about elemental composition in general increases year by year, elemental analysis becomes increasingly important. In this sense, the development of rapid, simple and sensitive methods that can be used in routine analysis is of special interest.

Sample preparation methods are usually a necessary and very important step in chemical analysis. Acid digestion is the most common sample treatment for elemental determination in biological materials. Acid digestion requires a high energy input and the use of concentrated mineral acids. Moreover, nitrous vapours produced as a result of organic matrix destruction are highly carcinogenic and thus safety considerations must be taken into account. Additional disadvantages include the high costs, time and energy required. These shortcomings have led to the consideration of direct analytical methods verified by conventional methods, which are not environmentally friendly but sensitive. Green Analytical Chemistry's main goals are to develop rapid analytical procedures and sustainable analytical methods that can significantly reduce the use of concentrated mineral acids (e.g. nitric acid) required for sample digestion, the energy required to operate analytical equipment (e.g. plasma spectrometers), or gases.

Inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES),^[10,11] flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS),^[12] inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS),^[13,14] energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF),^[15] electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS),^[16] and total reflection X-ray fluorescence (TXRF)^[17–19] are commonly used spectroscopic techniques for elemental analysis of plant samples.

TXRF is a technique for elemental analysis that has recently become very attractive in many fields.^[20–23] Recent applications of TXRF in analysis of biological samples have shown it to be a rapid method for quantitative analysis with detection limits comparable to other atomic techniques commonly used for trace element analysis in biological samples, such as FAAS, and ICP-OES.^[24] An additional advantage of TXRF in the field of vegetation sample analysis is the possibility to prepare solid samples using simpler sample treatments such as the suspension of few milligrams of the powdered sample in an adequate disperser agent.

The aim of this study was the comparison of the results obtained in the determination of the content of essential elements such as Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in vegetation samples using different analytical approaches, including: i) suspension preparation and TXRF analysis,

ii) open digestion and FAAS analysis iii) microwave digestion and ICP-OES analysis. Moreover, in the case of TXRF analysis, two instruments equipped with different X-ray tubes (Mo and W) were employed in order to better demonstrated the real possibilities of TXRF systems for the analysis of vegetation samples. Analytical figures of merit for the target methods were estimated by the analysis of reference materials with a vegetal matrix and finally the different analytical approaches were used for the determination of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in herbal teas used by local people for medicinal purposes and available in local markets.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Reagents and materials

Stock solution of Ga 1,000 mg/L (in 5% nitric acid, TraceCERT[®], standard for ICP, Fluka) was used to prepare the internal Ga standard solution. Nitric acid ($\geq 69\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) and hydrogen peroxide solution ($\geq 30\%$, TraceSELECT[®], Sigma-Aldrich) were used for microwave digestion of the ground herbal teas samples. Ultrapure deionised water for dilution of stock solutions and digested samples was obtained from a Milli-Q purification system (Millipore Corp., Bedford, MA). Standard stock solutions of Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn (1,000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ in 2% nitric acid) were purchased from PerkinElmer (Waltham, MA, USA). Working standards in the appropriate concentration range for each element were prepared fresh daily by dissolving the stock solution in MilliQ water. Silicone solution in isopropanol (Serva GmbH & Co, Germany) was used to coat all the quartz glass disc reflectors (diameter: 30 mm, thickness: 0.1 mm) to obtain a hydrophobic film to facilitate sample deposition. All glassware used for standard preparation was soaked overnight in 15% nitric acid (p.a. Kemika, Zagreb, Croatia) and rinsed thoroughly with MilliQ water before use.

2.2 | Samples

A total of six herbal teas were collected from the local market (Sarajevo, BiH) in 2019 and stored at room temperature until the analyses were performed. The herbal teas analysed in this work are listed in Table 1. The samples were ground with a pestle and mortar and the sample powder was sieved through a 63 μm sieve.^[25] The powdered samples were stored in polyethylene tubes at room temperature until analysis.

To ensure the accuracy of the results obtained, the certified reference materials: NCS ZC 73013 (spinach)

from China National Analysis Centre for iron and steel and NIST 1573a (tomato leaves) from the Institute of National Institute of Standards and Technology were used.

2.3 | Sample preparation procedures

In the present contribution, two different sample treatment approaches were used for vegetation samples analysis. On the one hand, suspension preparation was employed in the case of TXRF analysis and acid digestion for FAAS and ICP-OES analysis. A summary of the main steps involved in the preparation of vegetation samples by TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES analysis is displayed in Figure 1 and specific details can be found in the next sections.

TABLE 1 Description and nomenclature of herbal teas samples

Sample	Plant
A	<i>Plantago major</i> (leaves)
C	<i>Urtica dioica</i> (seeds)
E	<i>Hypericum perforatum</i> (above ground part)
F	<i>Teucrium chamaedrys</i> (above ground part)
H	<i>Rosa canina</i> (fruit)
I	<i>Juniperus communis</i> (fruit)

2.3.1 | TXRF

The content of elements (Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn) in the collected samples of the herbal teas were determined using low power TXRF systems equipped with Mo and W X-ray tubes. For both, the samples were prepared as described in the work of Dalipi et al. 2016.^[19] Sample suspensions were prepared by weighing 20 mg of sample and adding 1 ml of deionised water with 10 µg Ga as an internal standard. Duplicates were prepared for each sample and sonicated for 5 min in an ultrasonic bath. Then, 10 µl of the sample with the internal standard was deposited on a quartz glass reflector and dried with an infrared lamp for later TXRF analysis. The diameter of the sample spot on the reflector was around 5 mm, which was adequate taking into account the volume spanned by the excitation beam and the detector viewing.^[19]

2.3.2 | FAAS

The protocol for wet digestion was carried out following a recently published paper.^[26] Approximately 250 mg of the sample was weighed into a glass beaker and 10 ml of 65% nitric acid was added to each sample. A magnetic stirrer was added for stirring to enhance the extraction of the organic and inorganic materials. The beaker was covered with a watch-glass to prevent evaporation of the solution and the sample was gently boiled on a

FIGURE 1 Summary of TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES methods for the analysis of herbal tea samples [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

laboratory hot plate until digestion was complete, approximately 3 hr. The sample was then allowed to cool. After cooling, the solution was quantitatively transferred to 25 ml volumetric flask, diluted to volume with deionised water and filtered through 0.45- μm Milipore before analysis. Three replicate digestions were performed for each sample.

2.3.3 | ICP-OES

Microwave acid digestion was used to prepare the herbal teas samples according to the method EPA 3052.^[27] The microwave oven used was a Speedwave XPERT (Berghof products & Instruments GmbH, Alemania). About 250 mg of the sample was mixed with 9 ml of nitric acid and 1 ml of hydrogen peroxide in a Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) vessel. The vessels were sealed and heated following a two-step digestion programme consisting of a first step of 5 min until reaching 180°C and a second step of 10 min at 180°C. After cooling, the digested sample solutions were transferred to a 25 ml flask and brought to volume with ultra-pure deionised water.

2.4 | Instrumentation

2.4.1 | TXRF analysis

TXRF analysis was performed using two benchtop TXRF systems (S2 Picofox, Bruker AXS Microanalysis GmbH, Berlin, Germany) equipped with Mo (17.5 keV, 50 kV, 600 μA) and W (35.0 keV, 50 kV, 1 mA) X-ray tube anodes. In both cases, characteristic radiation emitted by the elements present in the sample was detected using a silicon drift detector with a resolution of less than 149 eV at Mn-K α . Measurements performed using the Mo-TXRF system were performed at 600 s meanwhile a longer measurement time (2000s) was necessary to obtain a similar precision when using the W-TXRF system, as we demonstrated in a previous work.^[19]

Evaluation of the TXRF spectra and the calculation of the net peak areas of the analytes were performed using the commercial software linked to the systems (Mo system: Spectra Plus 7.5.3.0; W system: Spectra Plus 5.3).

Quantification was performed by internal standardisation using the following expression^[28]:

$$C_i = \left(\frac{N_i C_{is} S_{is}}{N_{is} S_i} \right)$$

where C_i is the analyte concentration, N_i is the analyte net peak area, C_{is} is the IS concentration, S_{is} is the

instrumental sensitivity for the IS, N_{is} is the IS net peak area, S_i is the instrumental sensitivity for the analyte.

2.4.2 | FAAS analysis

Determination of Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn content was carried out using a Perkin-Elmer Analyst 800 atomic absorption spectrophotometer with deuterium background correction under optimised measurement conditions with suitable hollow cathode lamps and at optimum flame height (air-acetylene). The results were recorded and processed using AAWinlab 32 software (PerkinElmer).

External calibration was applied for the determination of metals of interest. Good linearity was observed for all elements at the concentration intervals tested. The correlation coefficients were in the range $r^2 = 0.993$ – 0.999 . For each sample and procedure, three replicates were performed in independent working sessions. Precision for all results was less than 5% on average.

2.4.3 | ICP-OES analysis

The Agilent ICP-OES 5100 Synchronous Vertical Dual View (SVDV) spectrometer was used for elemental determination in plant microwave digests. The elemental wavelengths (nm) were: Mn (257.610), Fe (238.204), Cu (327.395), Zn (213.857). The plasma was operated with 12 L/min plasma gas and an axial configuration. The detector type was a silicon-based multichannel array CCD (charge coupled device). Other parameters were: 1200 W RF power, concentric nebuliser type and polychromatic wavelength selector. External calibration using matrix-matched standard was employed as quantification approach. Good linearity was observed for all elements at the concentration intervals tested.

2.5 | Data analysis

2.5.1 | Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using PrismGraphPad 9 (GraphPad Software, Inc., San Diego, CA) and XLStat (XLStat Software, New York, SAD). Measurements were performed in triplicate and the results were presented as the mean \pm SD. Analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) was used to test hypotheses about the differences between elemental contents and the herbal teas or the type of sample preparation for analysis. Hierarchical cluster analysis using Euclidean distances was performed. p values $< .05$ were considered statistically significant.

2.5.2 | Limits and detection and limits of quantification calculation

Limits of detection (LODs) and limits of quantification (LOQs) for TXRF analysis were estimated from the spectra parameters (background area, N_{bkg} and analyte net peak area, N_i) obtained for triplicate analysis of the NCS ZC73013 (spinach) and using the following expressions (recommended by the TXRF system manufacturer):

$$LOD = \frac{3C_i \sqrt{N_{\text{bkg}}}}{N_i} \quad LOQ = \frac{10C_i \sqrt{N_{\text{bkg}}}}{N_i},$$

where C_i is the concentration of a given analyte; N_{bkg} is the background area and N_i is the analyte net peak area.

LODs and LOQs for FAAS and ICP-OES analysis were determined using the expression displayed below. As it is shown, in both cases, intercept and $S_{y/x}$ values of the regression line obtained in the analysis of a set of calibration standards were used to estimate LODs and LOQs:

$$LOD = y_B + 3s_B \rightarrow \text{where } y_B \text{ is the intercept and } s_B \text{ is the slope of the regression line}$$

$$LOQ = y_B + 10s_B \rightarrow \text{where } y_B \text{ is the intercept and } s_B \text{ is the slope of the regression line.}$$

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Analytical capabilities of TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES for vegetal sample analysis

In a first stage, to check the capability of suspension preparation and TXRF analysis for the determination of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in vegetal samples, LODs and LOQs were calculated analysing the certified reference material NCS ZC73013 (spinach).

Obtained results are reported in Table 2. For comparison purposes, LODs and LOQs for FAAS and ICP-OES are also included. As it is shown, for all the elements of interest, concentrations at the low mg/kg level can be detected regardless of the TXRF systems employed. However, LODs for the Mo-TXRF system is one order of magnitude lower. This fact is associated with a better sensitivity of Mo-TXRF system for mid-Z elements (i.e. Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn) in comparison with W-TXRF instrumentation.^[29] This is not a major drawback for elements present at higher concentrations in plant samples

TABLE 2 Limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) for the different analytical approaches considered, including suspension preparation and TXRF analysis (using Mo and W X-ray tubes) and sample digestion followed by FAAS and ICP-OES analysis

Limits of detection (mg/kg)	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn
TXRF (W X-ray tube)	9	6	3	3
TXRF (Mo X-ray tube)	0.6	0.4	0.3	0.2
FAAS	0.6	1.2	0.2	0.1
ICP-OES	0.5	1.6	0.4	0.4
Limits of quantification (mg/kg)	Mn	Fe	Cu	Zn
TXRF (W X-ray tube)	29	19	10	10
TXRF (Mo X-ray tube)	2	1.3	1	0.7
FAAS	2.1	3.9	1.5	1.3
ICP-OES	1.5	4.7	1.2	1.2

(i.e. Mn, Fe and Zn) but the quantification of elements present at lower concentrations (i.e. Cu) it is limited when using the W-TXRF method proposed (see Section 3.2 for additional details). It is also interesting to remark that LOQs values for Mo-TXRF method are similar or even better than those associated with FAAS and ICP-OES methods.

The accuracy of the results obtained with the different analytical approaches (suspension + TXRF; digestion + FAAS and microwave digestion + ICP-OES) was evaluated by analysing the reference materials NCS ZC73013 (spinach) and NIST 1573a (tomato leaves). As it is shown in Table 3, concentrations of the elements determined by all methods were in agreement with the certified values for most of the measurements. Only in the case of the W-TXRF method it was not possible to quantify Cu content since the certified concentration was slightly lower than the LOQ determined (see Table 2). The one-way test ANOVA applied to the analysed and certified values of the certified reference material, showed that the results were not statistically different at the significance level of p -values <0.05 . The recovery percentages of the individual elements ranged from 85 to 112% (W-TXRF), 97 to 113% (Mo-TXRF), 86 to 106% (FAAS) and 80 to 90% (ICP-OES). Lower recoveries were found in the case of Mn and Fe when using FAAS or ICP-OES methods, probably due to the fact that some elements are associated with the silica matrix and there is inefficient extraction occurs when HNO_3 and HNO_3 : H_2O_2 (9:1) are used as extractants.^[30–33] It is also interesting to mention that the Mn concentration in the reference material was really close to the LOQ for the W-TXRF method (see Table 2).

TABLE 3 Results obtained for the determination of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in certified reference materials using TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES analysis

Element	NCS ZC73013—Spinach			NIST 1573a—tomato leaves		
	TXRF (W)	ICP-OES	Certified	TXRF (Mo)	FAAS	Certified
Mn	34 ± 6	36 ± 2	41 ± 3	238.4 ± 5.6	212 ± 3	246 ± 8
Fe	600 ± 100	400 ± 20	540 ± 20	370 ± 20	350 ± 20	368 ± 7
Cu	<LOQ ^a	8.0 ± 0.1	8.9 ± 0.4	5.3 ± 0.5	5 ± 0.3	4.7 ± 0.1
Zn	35.7 ± 0.8	31 ± 2	35 ± 2	31 ± 1	31.2 ± 1.4	30.9 ± 0.7
Recovery (%)	85–112	80–90		97–113	86–106	

Note: Results are expressed as mean concentration values of three replicates with the associated SD (in mg/kg).

^aLOQ: 10 mg/kg (see Table 2).

TABLE 4 Comparison of analytic characteristics of TXRF, ICP-OES and FAAS for the analysis of vegetation samples

Characteristic	TXRF ^a	ICP-OES	FAAS
Multielemental analysis	Yes (simultaneous)	Yes	No
Screening capability	Yes	No	No
Amount of sample	10–50 mg	100–500 mg	100–500 mg
Sample treatment	Suspension/digestion	Digestion	Digestion
Quantification	Internal standardisation	External calibration	External calibration
Total analysis time ^b	15–40 min	2 hr	5 hr
Consumables	Not required	High-purity Ar	High-purity gases
Cooling media	Not required	Water cooling	Not required
Cost per analysis	Low	High	Medium

^aTXRF systems equipped with low-power X-ray tubes (50 W max.).

^bTotal analysis time: sample preparation + analysis + calibration.

Regarding the precision, average relative SDs were higher for suspension preparation and TXRF analysis (W-TXRF: 2–17%; Mo-TXRF: 2–10%) in comparison with FAAS/ICP-OES analysis (ICP-OES: 1.5–6%; FAAS: 1.6–6%). This fact can be related with the inhomogeneity of the suspension and also the deposition of the solid sample on the reflector as it has been pointed in recent publications dealing with the solid suspension analysis by TXRF.^[34] Despite of the lower precision of TXRF in comparison with FAAS and ICP-OES methods, the TXRF method presents also some interesting advantages in the field of vegetation sample analysis including a simpler sample treatment and quantification approach as well as a reduction of measuring costs and harmful reagents (see Table 4). So, depending on the final purpose of the analysis it can be a sustainable and fast analytical alternative to the most commonly used ones involving a previous digestion of the sample and ICP-OES or FAAS analysis. As it is shown in Table 4, the amount of sample required for TXRF analysis involving suspension preparation is about 10 times lower compared to the amount of sample needed in other spectroscopic methods. This fact can be

an advantage in case of vegetal mass-limited samples (i.e. soybean root and shoots).^[35] Nevertheless, it is important to ensure a good homogeneity of the original vegetal sample to obtain reliable results. For that usually a reduction of the particle size <75 µm is required before preparing the suspension.

3.2 | Application of TXRF, FAAS and ICP-OES for Zn, Cu, Mn and Fe determination in herbal teas

Once evaluated the analytical capabilities of the methods, they were used to determine the concentration of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in several herbal tea samples.

In Figure 2, as an example, the TXRF spectrum obtained in the analysis of the herbal tea sample A (see Table 1 for details) is displayed. As it is shown, information displayed from the spectra can be especially useful for rapid “screening” of multielemental composition of the vegetal samples. This is a clear advantage of TXRF over ICP-OES and FAAS analysis.

FIGURE 2 TXRF spectrum obtained in the analysis of the herbal tea sample A (analytical conditions: 20 mg, 1 ml ultrapure water, 10 μ g Ga [IS], 10 μ l sample deposition volume, 2000s, W X-ray tube, 50 W) [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

Results obtained for the determination of Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn in the target samples are shown in Figure 3. Concentrations of the elements are given on a dry weight basis and each result is the mean of three sample measurements. As it can be seen, in general good agreement was found between the results obtained by the studied methods. It is interesting to note that Mn concentrations for samples C, F and I and Fe concentration in sample I are really close to LOQs associated with the W-TXRF method (see Table 2). Likewise, Cu concentrations determined in samples A, F, H and I by the W-TXRF method were lower than 10 mg/kg (LOQ), and therefore, the determined concentration using this method are not included in Figure 3.

All herbal teas samples contained significant concentrations of essential elements (Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn). However, the content of all tested elements differed significantly among the tested plant species. The concentration differences obtained can be explained by the different plant species, i.e. their botanical part, the mobility of the elements within the plant, the mineral composition of the soil in which they are grown and the absorption capacities, as well as some other anthropogenic pollution sources.^[14,36]

Mn and Fe are elements present in the highest concentrations and their values vary. The concentrations of Mn and Fe were in the range of 22.4–86.4 mg/kg and 15.3–285.7 mg/kg, respectively, which is in agreement with the literature data.^[4,37–39] The results obtained in this study are in agreement with previous reports by^[40,41] indicating that the plant is an accumulator of Mn. The high Mn content may be due to the pesticides used to treat the soil in which the plant grows and the cultivation

of plants in industrial and residential areas, which are rich in Mn due to its use as a fuel additive. Considering the important role of Mn on the hormonal, nervous and enzymatic systems, the consumption of Mn-rich herbal teas may affect the normal metabolism of humans.

The Fe concentrations in the studied samples showed maximum values compared to the other elements. The highest Fe content was found in sample A, 285.7 mg/kg, and the lowest in sample I, 15.33 mg/kg, which is as expected. As essential elements, Cu and Zn are integral components of many enzymes such as superoxide dismutase, lysyl oxidase and ceruloplasmin, which play an important role in antioxidant defence.

Concentrations of Cu and Zn ranged from 2.1–16.6 and 12.4–78.73 mg/kg, respectively. The determined average concentration of zinc is about three times higher than the determined average concentration of copper, which is in agreement with previous studies.^[2,37,42,43] Fe, Zn and Cu are the elements present in considerably significant concentration and this may be correlated with the antioxidant activity of these elements.

In order to study if it was possible to classify the herbal tea samples based on their chemical composition, a cluster analysis was applied to the data obtained by using the aforementioned analytical methods. Euclidean distances were used to calculate the similarities of the samples and a hierarchical agglomerative procedure to form clusters. The obtained results are presented in dendrogram format in Figure 4. In general, for all of the studied methods, the samples were clustered into two groups (with similarity values of about 75% for FAAS and ICP-OES and of about 70% for TXRF methods, respectively) corresponding to the mineral content in a particular type of herbal tea. From the point of view of metal content, the first group contains herbal teas A, C and F, while the second group contains herbal teas E, H and I. The first group of herbal teas had the highest concentration of Fe and also higher concentration of Zn. It is interesting to note that the grouping among the samples in the first group is slightly different in the case of W-TXRF method, surely due to the proximity of the concentrations levels of the elements quantified in the herbal tea samples with the estimated LOQs (see Table 2). The second group of herbal teas (H and I only) had the lowest concentrations of all the elements studied. Herbal tea, E showed a lower correlation with the others. In this studied sample, the determined concentrations for Cu, Zn and Mn were more than twice as high as the determined concentrations in all other studied samples. Only the content of Fe was twice lower compared to the first group of samples from the defined cluster.

According to the results, this indicates a possible relationship between the clustering of the variables and the

FIGURE 3 Comparison of elemental content in different herbal teas using TXRF (Mo/W X-ray tubes), ICP-OES and FAAS methods. Error bars correspond to the SD of triplicate analysis [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

FIGURE 4 Dendrogram of the performed cluster analysis on the elemental content of the analysis herbal teas using FAAS, ICP-OES and TXRF methods [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

origin of the samples. It is clear that different plants can be grouped according to their element concentrations, but in this study, the focus is not on the origin of the elements in the herbal tea, so there is insufficient evidence on the origin of the metal contents, such as the mineral composition of the soil and the absorption capacities, as well as some other anthropogenic sources of pollution.

4 | CONCLUSION

This study gives an overview of the potential and limitations of TXRF in comparison with FAAS and ICP-OES methods for the determination of essential elements (Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn) in vegetation samples.

In addition to the instrumental characteristics of TXRF systems (simultaneous multielemental information, microanalytical capability and low operating costs), the technique also allows the possibility to carry out the analysis of plant samples by suspension of few milligrams of the sample in an adequate disperser. This is an interesting feature since the digestion step required in FAAS and ICP-OES analysis can be avoided and thus the consumption of reagents and the total analysis time is significantly reduced. An additional advantage is the simple quantification by internal standardisation and the possibility to get rapid and screening information about the

essential elements in the vegetation samples. It was found that LODs and quantification for Mn, Fe, Cu and Zn using the Mo-TXRF method were one order of magnitude lower than those obtained when using the TXRF method but with a W X-ray tube system. This is not a major drawback for elements present at concentration levels higher than 30 mg/kg in plant samples (i.e., Mn, Fe and Zn) but it is a limitation for a reliable quantification of elements such as Cu that are present at lower concentration levels (~10 mg/kg or lower). Finally, it is interesting to remark that similar results in terms of accuracy were obtained by the studied analytical approaches but the precision of the results obtained by suspension preparation and TXRF analysis was worse in comparison with FAAS/ICP-OES analysis. Nevertheless, depending on the final purpose of the analysis, TXRF can be a sustainable and fast analytical alternative to the most commonly used ones involving a previous digestion of the sample.

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

"The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request".

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